

Figure S1

Figure S1. Removal of cell debris. **A)** The image of single nuclei suspension preparation. **B)** Flow cytometry showing the majority of the suspension were nuclei and clear separation between the nuclei and the cell debris.

Figure S2

Figure S2. FACS-sorting control and gating. **A)** Signal intensity of GFP in WT mouse brain samples and Sun1 flox | Emx1-Cre (+) mouse brain samples. **B)** Signal intensity of GFP in a representative Sun1 flox | Emx1-Cre (+) mouse brain sample. **C)** FACS-sorting for Sun1 flox | Emx1-Cre (+) mouse brain sample (control sample) without anti-NeuN-PE Ab staining. **D)** FACS-sorting for Sun1 flox | Emx1-Cre (+) mouse brain sample with anti-NeuN-PE Ab staining.

Figure S3

Figure S3. Confirmation of high-quality CUT&RUN libraries. **A)** Fragment size distribution for each sample. The dashed and solid lines represent for two biological replicates, respectively. **B)** Correlation between biological replicates for each histone modification in excitatory and inhibitory neurons. **(C-F)** The signals of histone modifications and IgG in peak regions of H3K27ac (**C**), H3K4me1 (**D**), H3K4me3 (**E**) and H3K27me3 (**F**).

Figure S4

Figure S4. Correlation between CUT&RUN data in this study and ChIP-seq data from (Mo et al., Neuron, 2015) for excitatory neurons.

Figure S5

Figure S5. Comparison of histone modifications (A) and EGR1 binding (B) between excitatory and inhibitory neurons. The differential peak regions colored in blue and red were determined by “result” function in the DESeq2, with thresholds “ $\text{padj} \leq 0.05$ ” and “ $\text{FoldChange} \geq 2$ ” or “ $\text{FoldChange} \leq 0.5$ ” (see Methods).

Figure S6

Figure S6. Scatter plot showing the proportion changes of TFs' motif at active promoters of excitatory neurons compared with inhibitory neurons. For each motif, the percentage of active promoters containing this motif was calculated for excitatory and inhibitory neurons, separately. The promoter containing difference for each motif in two neuronal subtypes is shown in y-axis.

Figure S7

Figure S7. scRNA-seq and snATAC-seq data analysis during mouse brain development. A) Examples showing chromatin accessibility surrounding neuronal marker genes during brain development. **B)** Expression of neuronal marker genes related to A). **C and D)** Expression clustering analysis for EXC- (C) and INH-predominant (D) EGR1 peaks associated genes. **E and**

F) GO enrichment analysis for genes showing similar expression pattern with *Egr1* among all EXC- (E) and INH-predominant (F) EGR1 peaks associated genes.